

THE RISING FOCUS OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM ON HIGHER EDUCATION - A FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Emergence of Quality Education in India has become a predominant essential factor for each and every educational institutions in India in order to differentiate and develop the competency themselves they are relying on technological advances. Learning Management System is one among that technological innovation which was brought in to education sector to provide a unique kind of experience to their respective stake holders using it. Information Technology can be rightly said as an important component for innovation as it rightly enables concept of Electronic-Learning and it can provide certain conditions for an organization to be able to work with new businesses with an enriched processes. In today's academic scenario, the educational institutions are striving themselves to finding the right combination of learners, teachers and their respective systems and protocols to manage the learning Environment. In this context, Learning Management Systems (LMS) creates a communication and interaction path between learners and teachers in virtual environment for Educational Purposes. This conceptual paper majorly focuses on the emerging and rising technology learning management system as a competitive tool which strategically creates a unique educational platform for teachers and learners in a dominant manner. Also, through which the researchers would like to identify and examine the needs, importances, benefits, issues and challenges faced by the organizations in order to successfully implement Learning Management System into their core business services.

KEYWORDS: Learning Management System, Higher Education, Etc.,

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the current scenario, Learning Management System (LMS) in higher education plays a major and vital

role among the educational institutions worldwide, where in these Learning Management System are used to enhance learning sessions in the most appropriate and effective manner, so that teaching and learning would be an different kind of experience felt by both the teachers and learners community. In our day today technology transformation, where in the traditional way of teaching and learning would be replaced through the introduction of enhanced Learning Management System (LMS). These Learning Management System can also be known as Virtual Learning Environment, where in these Virtual Learning Environment mainly functions through web based interface which is used for content delivery and also helps in terms of various reporting through which learners performance can be measured.

2. Significant Importance and Need of Learning Management System (LMS) in Higher Educational Environment :

The Usage of Learning Management System in the educational environment has overcome lot of difficulties between the learner and teacher, in fact the relationship between them become more stronger than ever before because of the increasing interaction and assessing the quality of information readily available for the learner to take it away from anyplace in the world provided they do have quality internet connection. The Emergence of Technology paved a way in the Educational Environment to make use of this Learning Management System in a wider manner, where in it has changed the way of teaching and learning in many educational institutions since the earlier 1990's (Pishva, D., Nishantha, G.G.D. and Dang, H. A., 2010). This paved a way between to the technology and education gets integrated to each other and provides a new kind of experience to their stake holders in a most predominant manner. As a result, the communication between the learner and teacher increased, at the same time, it raised to a new kind of challenges upcoming and started to prevail in the field of education. (Pishva, D., Nishantha, G.G.D. and Dang, H. A., 2010).

E-learning plays an important role in the field of education, and its need and importance increase every day. Learning environments can take a myriad of distinct forms. Learning management systems (LMS) have emerged as a major platform to support effective learning platform, where as these learning management systems are used widely throughout Higher Education Institutions (HEI) on various aspects and the need to know and understand its adoption and usage arises.

Fig.No.1. Various Aspects of Implementing Learning Management System in Education

Global Learning Management System (LMS) Market Revenue Share By Geography, 2015 (US\$ Mn)

Source: TMR Analysis, October 2016

Fig.No.2. Global Learning Management System (LMS) Market Revenue Share

3. Benefits Of Learning Management System:

- The learner can get access to the information from anywhere at any time.
- Most modern Learning Management Systems have developed mobile applications through which learners can access e-learning content on any device.
- All the course materials are available at a central location where in the learners are able to access and exchange various resources.
- All the Learners will have a quick and vibrant communication. Their opinions are shared among themselves within their learning community members.
- This Virtual Learning Environment keeps the Learner and Teacher to have a strong relationship to get and share information in order to enhance quality education.
- The Learner will certainly have new kind of learning experience through learning management system and keep them more involved to the learning

environment. In addition to that it saves more time for the learner to search and find information apart from the most generic way through which fast learning can be ensured with an appropriate content.

7 BENEFITS OF ELEARNING

Fig.No.3. Benefits of Learning Management System (LMS)

4. Major Trends, Issues and Challenges of Implementing the Learning Management System in Higher Education Sector:

In this modern era, most of educational institutions have started to use Learning Management Systems actively for all specific needs and peculiarities of business. There are so many varieties of Learning Management Systems available out there with certain competency, which allow them to build their own courses by using on pre-built content templates, extensions, features, and inserting media. Here the researcher tries to inhibit the various challenges of Learning Management Systems (LMSs). Also, when building an E-Learning solution, ensure it will have high level of scalability, user-friendly interface and simple reporting. As lack of these features is one of the main reasons that users do not want to use Learning Management System to a certain level. **Sergey Valuy (2017)**. Here are some common Learning Management System implementation challenges that one should consider before going fourth and purchasing one.

Fig.No.4. Challenges of Implementing Learning Management System

Fig.No.5. Trends of Learning Management System

5. Current Scenario of Learning Management System in Higher Education

On those earlier days of learning, learners were majorly associated with educational institutions like schools, colleges and universities. After a period of time, learners perceived that teaching and learning is over, once they had graduated and moved out of the university. Then at certain point of time learners start to believe that continuous learning and teaching for the whole life was associated with the teacher's community. At present the total scenario of teaching and learning has changed, where the knowledge is rapidly evolving in a manner that for one to remain productive. In this context the learner needs to learn continuously and progressively irrespective of his profession that he holds up with in order to keep himself knowledge enriched and to remain competent in this changing business environment (**Anita Chandwani; Shraddhaanil Kumar**). Continuous and Progressive learning is very much essential and significant due to frequent change in the technology (**Anita Chandwani; Shraddhaanil Kumar**) and to keep ourselves ready in order to adapt such technological change.

In this 21st century, most of the educators realized that learners of this generation are completely different from those of earlier generation what we had earlier in terms expectations, objectives, perception and reality in the way they approach the problem and in turn take correct decisions too. The learners of this generation are generally demanding a change in the classroom teaching because of their ability to gather information faster than any other generation (**Ahmad Tasnim Siddiqui; Mehedi Masud, 2012**) given the resources available today for use in the classroom, such as overhead projector, LCD projector and so on. The most toughest job is to integrate all available effective resources into a defined tool. In order to sort these major differences in

teaching and learning, learning management system is such a kind of tool which predominantly addresses real life challenges of faculties, learners and educators. Learning Management System is an enriched and enhanced powerful tool which helps the classroom teaching more effective and efficient way to the learners and teachers.

At present the world which we live in are more competitive, where education has become more global need and learners are looking for major innovation in learning with the help of technological revolution and usage of worldwide web (Internet) like submitting online assignments, reading online lecture notes, giving online exam etc. Electronic-Learning is a kind of learning experience where most learners expect and now a day's learners frequently use internet to access social media websites like Facebook, Orkut, Google Plus (**Monarch Media Inc. 2010**) to keep themselves updated in terms of communication perspective and in order to share their views and opinions to outside world. This in turn encourage all children to reach up to their fullest potential (**Gretchen Rhines Cheney, Betsy Brown Ruzzi and Karthik Muralidharan (2005)**). In this changing scenario teachers are well qualified and even then classroom has become an outdated way of learning to these upcoming generation, these became a predominant challenge for the educators to offer and bring a different kind of experience these generation learners they do expect from these educators. For which educators got a solution through the adaptation of Learning Management System, where it overcomes all the deficiencies and it became a new technological platform wherein both teacher and learner would get the complete fullest satisfaction towards teaching and learning.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Learning Management System (LMS) works as a lever for the broader scope for improvement in teaching and learning in the educational environment. Self-growth and career development of learners are very much assured through Learning Management System. Massive Open Online Courses, NPTEL, Apna Courses, Coursera, Future Learn, Moodle helped learners to understand the importance of Learning Management System. The purpose of knowledge and awareness of Learning Management System is to improve quality of education in various aspects, by supporting educational environment in the knowledge gained by the learners. A Learning Management System learner can create wonder in career and life. It is need of hrs.

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